

Lithium-Powder Based Electrodes Modified with ZnI₂ for Enhanced Electrochemical Performance of Lithium-Metal Batteries

Aleksei Kolesnikov,¹ Dong Zhou,¹ Martin Kolek,^{1,*} Juan Pablo Badillo Jimenez,¹ Peter Bieker,^{1,2} Martin Winter,^{1,3,**,z} and Marian Cristian Stan^{1,z}

¹MEET Battery Research Center, University of Münster, 48149 Münster, Germany

²Institute of Physical Chemistry, University of Münster, 48149 Münster, Germany

³Helmholtz-Institute Münster (HI MS), IEK-12, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, 48149 Münster, Germany

Lithium-powder electrodes, prepared via paste casting method using lithium powder and polyisobutylene (PIB) as a binder, were investigated for their electrochemical properties in lithium-metal cells. The electrode paste casting method allows preserving the spherical shape of lithium-powder particles during processing to electrodes. However, these lithium-powder based electrodes suffer from poor active material utilization, as electronic isolation of lithium particles during the lithium electrodisso- lution process was observed to occur. In order to improve the lithium inter-particle contact as well as the contact with the current collector, a simple and effective chemical modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes was considered. Using a cementation reaction with ZnI₂, the growth of a Li-Zn intermetallic (“alloy”) between the lithium-powder particles and the surface of the lithium powder, lead to an increase of the active material utilization and overcame the side reactions due to lithium electrodisso- lution. Besides increasing the active material utilization, such simple chemical modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes improved the electrochemical performance resulting in more stable cycling behavior with low polarization and longer cycle life in both Li||Li-symmetric and Li||NMC 622 cells.

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The recent efforts to increase the energy density^{1–3} of lithium ion batteries (LIBs), accompanied by reducing the costs (\$/kWh),⁴ are focused on alternatives of the state-of-the-art electrode materials. On the anode side, the material of choice that is still graphite,^{5,6} is now becoming complemented by silicon^{7,8} or depending on the application may be in the future replaced by lithium metal,^{9,10} both having considerably higher specific capacities than graphite/carbon. As cathode materials, lithiated nickel-cobalt-manganese layered oxide (NMC) and lithiated nickel-cobalt-aluminum layered oxide (NCA) are considered for the next at least 10 years, but with lithium metal anodes also sulfur (S/C_{meso/micro} composite cathode) or oxygen (gas diffusion electrode) represent an alternative.^{11,12} The rechargeable battery concepts based on these cathode materials (lithium insertion materials, sulfur and oxygen) with lithium metal as anode are known as lithium-metal batteries (LMBs^{13,14}) and were already studied before the LIBs.¹⁵ As like LIBs, LMBs constitute a large family of cell chemistries. Recently, the revival of this battery cell type was proven by the continuing attempts to implement rechargeable lithium-metal cells in various applications.^{16–18} In order to reach a breakthrough enabling commercialization, several challenges need to be faced, where viable solutions are required.^{19,20} Among the various addressed solutions, the suppression of high surface area lithium formation (HSAL²¹), is essential for the safety and performance characteristics improvement of LMBs. Hereby, the initial nature and shape of the lithium metal (powder vs. foil) plays probably the most important role in diminishing the effects of uncontrolled lithium electrodeposition, formation of HSAL and lithium deposits with needle-like “dendritic” structures being the most detrimental.^{22–24} Among practical applications,²⁵ the use of self-standing lithium-powder based electrodes as anodes in energy storage and conversion applications is very scarce, since the focus was always concentrated on the practical implementation of lithium-powder material. For such reason, the application of lithium-metal powder was mainly as sacrificial active material²⁶ for the chemical or electrochemical pre-lithiation^{26–29} of high capacity anode materials³⁰ in LIBs, LMBs,³¹ and also in lithium-ion capacitors (LICs).^{32–34}

Lithium-powder based electrodes could offer several benefits for the application in LMBs. Due to the higher surface area compared

to lithium foil, electrodes with lithium-metal-powder can reduce the effective current density during the lithium electrodeposition (“plating”) and electrodisso- lution (“stripping”) processes.¹² Additionally, lithium-metal-powder is preferred as a source of lithium in composite lithium-metal electrodes since it eases “dosing” of the lithiation mass control.^{35,36} Fan et al. prepared a novel composite anode material by mixing hard carbon and stabilized lithium metal powder (SMLP) followed by processing using the conventional doctor blade technique to a high porosity electrode.³⁷ The resulted electrode porosity turned out to be beneficial for the lithium electrodisso- lution and electrodeposition behavior in such composite anodes. Furthermore, the investigations in lithium-metal-powder||sulfur cells (Li_p||S) indicated that the improvement of the cycling behavior of the Li_p||S cells arises also from the use of composite lithium-powder electrodes. It was hypothesized, that the porosity within the bulk of the anode was able to reduce the lithium polysulfide redox shuttle mechanism that further lead to the formation of a uniform, less dense film with neat appearance at the cathode side.³⁷ In another study, the addition of SMLP to a S/C_{micro} composite cathode, followed by calendaring, resulted in an improvement of cycling stability and Coulombic efficiency (CE) of such Li||S cells.³⁸ The cyclic voltammetry measurements using pre-lithiated cathodes indicated that the large irreversible capacity during the first cycle is completely compensated by the addition of SMLP, while an increase of capacity was also observed. The electrochemical performance using a C-rate of 0.1C resulted in almost 100% CE, with a delivered capacity of 650 mAh/g for more than 900 cycles.³⁸ Yersak et al. investigated the role of SMLP addition to a Si-Ti-Ni alloy anode when coupled with a S/C composite cathode.³⁹ The results showed that the addition of SMLP offsets the Coulombic inefficiencies by providing a buffer effect for the depth of discharge of the Si-Ti-Ni alloy anode, thus improving the cycling stability.³⁹

Superior electrochemical performances with prolonged cycling life and better rate characteristics of lithium-metal cells were shown using high surface area lithium-metal-powder based electrodes.³¹ For such reasons, lithium-metal powder is often advocated to replace lithium-metal foil.^{40,41} However, lithium-powder based electrodes are characterized by severe morphological changes as the pristine particle shape is difficult to be maintained during continuous lithium electrodisso- lution and electrodeposition processes. As a result, the formation of HSAL leads to increased electrolyte consumption, solid electrolyte interphase (SEI⁴²) formation and accumulation of “dead lithium”, re-

*Electrochemical Society Student Member.

**Electrochemical Society Fellow.

^zE-mail: martin.winter@uni-muenster.de; marian.stan@uni-muenster.de

sulting in a decrease of the active material utilization, decrease of the CE and of cycle life of these electrodes. Such processes occur already within the initial cycles and continue upon further cycling, leading to an imminent cell failure. The lithium-metal-powder's morphology changes upon the amount of lithium that is electrodissoved,⁴³ leading to the formation of hemispherical lithium particles. Finally, the formation of HSAL is further accentuated on these particles, irrespective of the current density.⁴⁴ Some attempts to overcome such issues considered compressing the lithium-powder based electrodes.⁴⁵ Using a high level of compression (60% of the initial electrode thickness), improved cycling performance with reduced and stable potential/voltage polarization were shown in Li||Li-symmetric cells.⁴⁶ Nevertheless, even with the loss of pristine ("customized") lithium-metal-powder morphology, the mechanical modification^{21,47} of lithium-metal electrodes represents an approach that can be used to improve the energy density of LMBs. With increasing interest in LMBs, it is foreseen that the practical application of lithium-metal-powder will not be further only limited to pre-lithiation, but also in future applications that require the use of lithium-metal electrodes with controlled capacity.

In this work, we report an approach to increase the active material utilization in lithium-metal electrodes prepared with lithium-metal-powder. Previous reports indicated that the interphase (artificial SEI, a-SEI), formed at the surface of the lithium-metal foil electrodes when kept in contact with a metal salt dissolved in an organic solution, renders a homogeneous distribution of the lithium-ions during the electrochemical process.⁴⁸ Herein, the chemical modification of the lithium-powder electrodes carried out using a solution of ZnI₂ in tetrahydrofuran (THF) is reported. The electrochemical and morphological characterizations of the modified lithium-powder based electrodes were carried out in order to assess the effect of the chemical modification. Improved electrochemical performances were showed by the modified lithium-powder based electrodes. These modified electrodes present a stable cycling behavior with low overvoltage for the lithium electrodeposition and electrodissoved processes (in Li||Li-symmetric cells), while a noticeable difference when compared to the un-modified lithium-powder electrodes was observed in full cells with NMC 622 as cathode material (when the potential of the anode was also recorded using the reference electrode).

Experimental

The lithium-powder based electrodes were prepared using the procedure described by Heine et al.²³ Lithium-metal-powder (d₉₀ < 50 μm, China Energy Lithium) was mixed with a solution of 3% (by weight) of polyisobutylene (PIB) in heptane (Sigma Aldrich, anhydrous 99%) and coated on dendritic Cu foil (18 μm, Schlenk Metal Foils GmbH & Co. KG). After drying, the electrodes with a final composition of 95 wt% active material and 5 wt% binder, were roll-pressed to 80 μm (70% of their initial thickness) using a bench top calendar machine (MTI Corp., MR100DC). The cathode material LiNi_{0.6}Mn_{0.2}Co_{0.2}O₂ (NMC 622, BASF) was mixed with a solution of poly(vinylidene) difluoride (PVdF, Solvay) in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, anhydrous, 99.5% Sigma-Aldrich) and conductive agent Super C65 (Imerys Graphite & Carbon) using an intensive mixer *Labormischer* R02 VAC (EIRICH EVACTHERM) to a final composition of 95:2:3 by weight (active material: conductive agent: binder). The slurry was coated on aluminum current collector, with a wet film thickness of 120 μm, leading to an average capacity per area of ≈1 mAh/cm². The electrode sheets were pre-dried at 70°C and subjected to calendaring (electrode porosities of ≈30%) and finally cut into disks (12 mm diameter) prior the final drying step, performed under vacuum (10⁻³ mbar) and at 120°C for 12 hours.

The inorganic coating was prepared by drop coating technique. For that, the lithium-powder based electrodes with a diameter of 12 mm were contacted with a 0.3 M solution of ZnI₂ (Sigma Aldrich, 98%) in tetrahydrofuran (THF, Sigma Aldrich, 99%) for 3 minutes. Afterwards, the reacted electrodes were washed several times with THF (20 mL) to remove the soluble salts and dried under vacuum for

15 minutes. All these procedures were carried out inside the dry room with a dew point of -50°C.

The electrochemical characterization of the unmodified (Li_p) and chemically modified (Li_{pce}) lithium-powder based electrodes was carried out either in 2-electrode cells (CR2032) for the capacity determination experiments and lithium charge/discharge cycling, and in 3-electrode cells (in-house cell design) for the Li||NMC 622 cells. Li||Li-symmetric cells were assembled using the unmodified and chemically modified electrodes and one layer of a polypropylene-based separator (Celgard 2500). For the electrode capacity evaluation measurements (Li||Cu cells), a separator stack, including 4 layers of non-woven polypropylene separators (Freudenberg, FS 2190) faced to the Cu-foil, and one layer of Celgard 2500 separator faced to the lithium side, was used. The 3-electrode Li||NMC 622 cells were assembled using the lithium-powder based electrodes as counter electrode (CE), and lithium-metal (China Energy Lithium) as reference electrode (RE) while the working electrode (WE) was the NMC 622 composite cathode. The electrodes were separated by one layer of Celgard 2500 separator. In all cases, the separator was soaked with 30 μL electrolyte LP47 (1 M LiPF₆ in EC:DEC 3:7 (w/w), BASF SE), except for the practical capacity determination measurements where 120 μL of electrolyte were used. Li||Li-symmetric cells were cycled using a current density of 0.1 mA/cm² with cutoff voltages of -1.5 V and 1.5 V. The Li||NMC 622 cells were charged and discharged at a constant current corresponding to 0.2C-rate (charge) and 1C-rate (discharge) between the potential limits 4.3 V and 3.0 V vs. Li/Li⁺ using a battery testing unit Maccor Series 4000 (Maccor Inc.). All the measurements were carried out at 20°C and all the cells were assembled inside a dry room (dew point -50°C).

The morphology of the lithium-powder based electrodes was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (Zeiss Auriga) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray detector (EDX, Oxford Instruments). The SEM images were recorded using an accelerating voltage of 3 kV and a working distance of 4 mm. Prior to the SEM measurements, the cycled electrodes were washed with ≈2 mL dimethyl carbonate (DMC) for three times and then dried in vacuum. For the cross-section investigations, the lithium-powder based electrodes were sliced using a razor blade. The structural composition of the chemically modified electrodes (Li_{pce}) was investigated by means of X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a AXS Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker) with a Cu K-α radiation (λ_{Cu} = 0.15418 nm) and equipped with a Lynx-Eye 1-dimensional Position Sensitive Detector (PSD). The patterns were recorded between 20 to 80 degree 2θ range using a step size of 0.02 degree and a time per step of 0.2 s. To carry out the measurements, the lithium-powder based electrodes were fixed on the sample holder (single crystal silicon) using a special tape in order to avoid the contact with air and moisture during the measurement (10 minutes).

Results and Discussion

The particle morphology of the as-received lithium-metal-powder before and after processing into electrodes is provided by the SEM images in Figure 1. The spherical shape and broad particle size distribution (5 to 50 μm) observed from Figures 1a and 1b for lithium-metal-powder, is further observed after the preparation of lithium-powder based electrodes (Figures 1c, 1d), thus the spherical shape of the particles was maintained during the mechanical processing to electrodes. This indicates that, the herein used electrode paste casting method, followed by slight electrode compression,⁴⁹ preserves the spherical shape of the lithium-powder particles after processing to lithium-powder based electrodes.

The broad particle size distribution can also provide advantages, resulting in a denser packing of the particles and improved inter-particle connection and higher active material loading of the prepared lithium-powder based electrodes. However, the preparation of lithium-powder based electrodes requires caution due to the reactivity of lithium-metal-powder (related to its high surface area) and fragility of the coating. Therefore, the characterization of lithium-powder based electrodes as well as the optimization of the preparation procedure is tricky.

Figure 1. Particle morphology of (a,b) the lithium-metal-powder and (c,d) lithium-powder based electrodes.

An advantage of the casting method is that by using an adjustable micrometer film applicator the thickness of the electrodes and thus the mass-loading can be precisely controlled. In contrast to the common LIB electrodes, the lithium-powder based electrodes contained no additional conductive agents, such as carbon black.⁵⁰⁻⁵² Therefore, the investigation of the electrochemical performance of these electrodes is crucial to elucidate their practical available capacity, also considering the difference in the particle size. The capacity of the lithium-powder based electrodes was determined by either using the mass-loading of active material (mg/cm^2) obtained by weighting of the electrodes (Table S1) or by means of lithium electrodisolution of a $\text{Li}_p||\text{Cu}$ cell (Figures 2a and S3). Figure 2 presents the voltage profile during the lithium electrodisolution of a lithium-powder based electrode

($\text{Li}_p||\text{Cu}$ cell) as well as the morphology change after the constant current experiment. The inset in Figure 2a provides a schematic description of the experiment that was conducted by electrodisolution of lithium from the lithium-powder based electrode (counter electrode) and electrodepositing on the Cu-foil (working electrode) using a constant current density of $0.5 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ down to the voltage cutoff value of -1.5 V was reached. The capacity of these electrodes calculated from the weighted mass of the active material is reported in Table S1.

The voltage profile of the lithium-powder based electrode shows an “activation” overvoltage; the cell voltage decreases to -0.32 V and then slowly increases to -0.2 V during the lithium electrodisolution process that accounted for almost $0.35 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$, before stabilizing to -0.2 V (Figure 2a). The voltage remained constant at this value for another $2.0 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$ before sharply decreasing to the voltage cutoff value that was set to -1.5 V . Such behavior is characteristic for a homogeneous lithium electrodeposition (and electrodisolution) while the following drop in cell voltage to -1.5 V indicates, that the amount of active lithium at the lithium-powder based electrode is shortened or even fully consumed. At the end of the experiment, a total amount of capacity equal to $2.3 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$ was obtained from the lithium-powder based electrode. Compared to the theoretical values given in Table S1, almost 1/4 of the lithium active material in this electrode could be electrochemically accessed (weighted capacity of $9.3 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$ vs. practical capacity of $2.3 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$). The evolution of the surface morphology of such electrodes after the electrodisolution process is also presented in Figures 2b, 2c. The SEM images indicate an inhomogeneous usage of lithium as some of the particles are completely consumed whereas others seem to be unreacted. To further investigate the reasons for the poor active material utilization, *post-mortem* analysis was carried out for the lithium-powder based electrodes from a $\text{Li}_p||\text{Li}_p$ -symmetric cell, where an amount of $1.0 \text{ mAh}/\text{cm}^2$ areal-capacity-equivalent of lithium was removed using a current density of $0.1 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$, and the results are provided in Figure S1. It is observed that in contrast to what was believed that lithium electrodisolution occurs only from the surface of the composite electrodes,⁴⁹ lithium electrodisolution is observed also for particles which are closer or in direct contact to the Cu-foil current collector (Figure S1e,f). Even more, the

Figure 2. Electrochemical (a) and morphological (b,c) investigation of the lithium-powder based electrode after lithium electrodisolution (lithium-powder electrode capacity evaluation) in 1 M LiPF_6 in EC:DEC 3:7 (w/w) at a current density of $0.5 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$.

Figure 3. Morphological and structural investigation of the lithium-powder based electrodes modified with ZnI_2 showing a,b) SEM image of electrode surface recorded at magnifications of $100\times$ and $500\times$, c) SEM cross-section image and d) the X-ray diffraction pattern.

SEM images of the lithium-powder based electrodes where lithium electrodeposition occurred (working electrode) in Figures S1b-d indicate an uneven coverage with lithium deposits (dendrites) in these electrodes. Therefore, the poor active material utilization seems to originate from non-uniform inter-particle contact and related non-uniform contact with the Cu-foil current collector.

An approach to improve the capacity utilization of lithium-powder based electrodes and to overcome the observed limitations that occur during the lithium electrodischarge was considered. The approach was based on a chemical modification of the lithium-powder electrodes using a 0.3 M solution of ZnI_2 in THF. The reaction between ZnI_2 and lithium-metal particles is expected to produce metallic Zn and LiI. While the former is electrochemically active with lithium and leads to the formation of a Li-Zn intermetallic, the latter is soluble in the organic solvent (THF) and thus will not be included in the composition of the cementation phase in these electrodes. This approach was also reported by Liang et al.³⁸ for lithium foil, but in their experiments ZnCl_2 was used instead of ZnI_2 . Nevertheless, side reactions (that consume active lithium) of the organic solvents and lithium-metal electrodes should not be neglected since this can further influence the nature of the cementation layer. The morphological and the structural characterization of such modified lithium-powder based electrodes denoted as Li_{pce} , is presented in Figure 3.

The SEM images in Figures 3a and 3b indicate a heterogeneous distribution of both reacted and unreacted lithium-powder particles. The cross-section SEM image in Figure 3c indicates that the reaction products between lithium-metal-powder and ZnI_2 accumulate within the inter-particle voids but also partially coat the surface of the lithium-powder particles. The XRD pattern of the Li_{pce} composite electrode (without the Cu-foil current collector) is provided in Figure 3d. The structural characterization reveals the presence of the Zn and a $\text{Li}_{0.02}\text{Zn}_{1.98}$ phase. However since the reflections from these two phases are identical, in Figure 3d only the $\text{Li}_{0.02}\text{Zn}_{1.98}$ phase is indicated, bearing in mind the environment in which such phases are present. Further experiments are provided in Figure S2 that further describes the reaction mechanism between lithium-metal-powder and the ZnI_2 in THF solution. Although the reaction between ZnI_2 and the

lithium-metal-powder occurred with the subsequent alloying reaction, the results presented in Figure 3 and S2 indicate a rather heterogeneous cover.

To investigate whether the chemical modification had any effect on the electrochemical performance of the lithium-powder based electrodes, especially on the delivered capacity, $\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}\|\text{Cu}$ cells were assembled and investigated. The results of these investigations are provided in Table S2 and Figure S3. The results indicated that the practical capacity of the modified lithium-powder based electrodes was $\approx 1/2$ from the calculated capacity based on the weight of the active material (including the weight of the Li-Zn phase). Comparing these results with those for the Li_p electrodes, it can be concluded that chemical modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes results in improved electrochemical behavior and in a higher active material utilization, i.e. 4.8 mAh/cm^2 as compared to 2.3 mAh/cm^2 for unmodified electrodes.

The cycling stability of the lithium-powder based electrodes in symmetric cells using the unmodified and the modified lithium-powder based electrodes was investigated. In the experiments presented in Figure 4, a current density of 0.1 mA/cm^2 was used with a voltage cutoff value of -1.5 V and 1.5 V , respectively. Using $\text{Li}_p\|\text{Li}_p$ - and $\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}\|\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}$ -symmetric cells, the voltage profiles during the lithium electrodeposition and electrodischarge can be compared, while the effect that the cathode material would play during such electrochemical processes is neglected. In Figure 4a, the comparison between the overvoltages during the lithium electrodeposition and electrodischarge indicate lower overvoltages for the Li_{pce} electrodes as compared to the unmodified electrodes. Furthermore, the cycling behavior of the modified lithium-powder based electrodes extends well above 350 cycles while the unmodified electrodes could only reach 75 cycles before the voltage profiles reached the cutoff voltage value of 1.5 V . A detailed comparison of the voltage profiles for selected cycles between the two electrodes is provided in Figures 4b and 4c. As mentioned, the voltage profiles during lithium electrodeposition and electrodischarge are affected by the chemical composition of the lithium-powder particle surface (e.g., native film and SEI). Figure 4b, shows that the voltage during the lithium electrodeposition and electrodischarge of the unmodified lithium-powder based electrodes become smaller with

Figure 4. Electrochemical investigations in Li||Li-symmetric cells, showing (a) the long term cycling at 0.1 mA/cm^2 of the non-modified (Li_p) and modified with ZnI_2 (Li_{pce}) lithium-powder based electrodes and the respective selected voltage profiles for (b) non-modified (Li_p) and (c) modified with ZnI_2 (Li_{pce}) lithium-powder based electrodes.

increasing cycling number. This is commonly observed for lithium-metal electrodes, when during the continuous breaking and formation of the SEI,^{53,54} the newly formed lithium-metal surface (containing HSAL) is not strongly passivated by the SEI.⁵⁵ Afterwards, in the 50th cycle the electrode degradation is more obvious by the variations in the voltage profiles. On contrary, the results in Figure 4c for the modified lithium-powder based electrodes do not indicate that such a behavior occurs. It is believed that through the modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes using ZnI_2 , the Li-Zn phase that is formed within the voids between the particles and partially covering the surface of the lithium-powder particles reduces the electrode polarization (overpotential). The electrochemical behavior of the modified lithium-powder based electrodes in Li_{pce} || Li_{pce} -symmetric cells during the first cycle is no different than that in the 100th cycle. In addition, the results in Figure 3d indicate that the active phase is a Zn-rich Li-Zn intermetallic, but no additional voltage plateaus were observed in these cells during the lithium electrodeposition that would represent a clear indication of an electrochemical reaction between the $\text{Li}_{0.02}\text{Zn}_{1.98}$ phase and lithium. Hence, an activation process where the $\text{Li}_{0.02}\text{Zn}_{1.98}$ phase is converted to LiZn intermetallic occurs during the addition of the electrolyte in the Li_{pce} || Li_{pce} -symmetric cells. The presence of the intermetallic phase increases then the electronic conductivity and also enhances the ionic transport path inside the electrode bulk.⁵⁶

In Figure 5, the schematic representation based on these observations for both the Li_p and Li_{pce} electrodes is provided. The schematic in Figure 5a shows that during the lithium electrodisolution in the Li_p electrodes, lithium is removed both from the surface of the electrode as well as from bulk, even the side facing the Cu-foil current

collector. This results in a local loss of electronic contact between particles and with the Cu-foil that further leads to reduced active material utilization. In Figure 5b, the cementation reaction with ZnI_2 , avoids the detrimental lithium electrodisolution through the accumulation of the reaction products within the electrode bulk and surface of the lithium-powder particles. This leads to a more homogeneous lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution reactions that further enhances the electrochemical performance. However, the chemical modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes with ZnI_2 does not preserve the lithium-powder particle morphology nor completely avoids the formation of HSAL deposits, although the formation is much more homogeneous, thus is probably more controllable.

In Figure 6 the electrochemical behavior of Li_p and Li_{pce} electrodes in 3-electrodes cells, using NMC 622 as a cathode material and lithium foil as reference electrode is displayed. In Figure 6a, it can be observed that the cells with unmodified lithium-powder based electrodes already show an erratic cycling behavior within the initial 20 cycles that leads to a premature failure. At contrast, the cells with modified lithium-powder based electrodes are able to reach almost 200 cycles before cell failure occurs while the cell voltage remains stable (Figure 6b). The potential profiles (Figures 6c and 6d) indicate that the overpotentials at the Li_p and Li_{pce} electrodes differ quite a lot. Such observation is in accordance to the previously observations already made for the Li||Li-symmetric cells, that the modified lithium-powder based electrodes perform superior than their unmodified correspondents. While the potential profiles of the NMC 622 cathodes are similar for both cells, there are crucial differences when the potential profiles of the Li_p electrode are compared (Figure 6c). In this case, the potential for the electrodisolution reaction increases in every cycle and reaches

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the behavior of the lithium-powder based electrodes during lithium electrodis-solution and electrodeposition.

a value >3 V vs. Li/Li^+ already after 100 hours (approximately 15 cycles) (Figure S4a). In further cycles, it approaches 5 V and the cell is stopped due to safety reasons. On the contrary, the chemically modified lithium-powder based electrodes (Figure 6d) demonstrate a clearly different behavior. During lithium electrodis-solution at 0.2C, within the initial three cycles (formation cycles at 0.2C/0.2C for the $\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}||\text{NMC}$ 622 cells), the overpotential is ≈ 100 mV. When the C-rate for the discharge process is changed from 0.2C to 1C, a local maximum of ≈ 250 mV with decreasing tendency of the overpotential and subsequent stabilization at <200 mV is observed (Figure S4b). These results also imply that the chemical modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes have a beneficial effect on the C-rate performance of the $\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}||\text{NMC}$ 622 cells.

Post-mortem analysis of the lithium-powder based electrodes after the first cycle in full cells were carried out and the results are shown in Figure 7. These investigations mainly focus on the morphological changes that occur with the lithium-powder based electrodes in $\text{Li}_{\text{p}}||\text{NMC}$ 622 cells and $\text{Li}_{\text{pce}}||\text{NMC}$ 622 cells during the first cycle. It is also expected to provide more detailed information on the reasons that could result in a depletion of the available lithium amount and thus leads to capacity fading and premature cell failure with lithium-powder based electrodes. In these experiments, the cells were charged up to 4.3 V vs. Li/Li^+ and discharged down to 3 V vs. Li/Li^+ . Figures 7a and 7b present the recorded potential profiles of both the cathode and the lithium-powder based electrode. Recurrently, it is indicated that the ZnI_2 modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes has little effect on the potential profile of the cathode material during the charge and discharge process (Figure 7a). Nevertheless, differences between the potentials of the two anodes are visible already within the first lithium electrodeposition process (Figure 7b). Figures 7c–7f present the morphological changes of the lithium-powder based electrodes after the first lithium electrodeposition and electrodis-solution processes.

Figure 6. Constant current measurements of the pristine (Li_{p}) and modified lithium-powder based electrodes (Li_{pce}) with NMC 622 as cathode, showing the (a) specific discharge capacity and Coulombic efficiency, (b) the cell voltage and the potential profiles vs. Li/Li^+ of the cells assembled with (c) Li_{p} anode and (d) Li_{pce} anode. The first three cycles were carried out at a C-rate of 0.2C/0.2C, while the cycling was continued with a C-rate of 0.2C/1C for the charged/discharge process.

Figure 7. Lithium-powder based electrodes after the first electrodeposition and electrodisolution process: (a) NMC 622 potential profile, (b) Li_p and Li_{pce} -potential profile, (c, d) unmodified lithium-powder based electrode after the first lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution and (e, f) ZnI_2 -modified lithium-powder based electrode after the first lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution.

It is surprising that in the case of the Li_p electrode, the lithium electrodeposition forms large, singular lithium deposits (Figure 7c). Also the removal of lithium from these electrodes during the discharge process leads to an inhomogeneous usage of the lithium (Figure 7d), that was previously also reported. However, more homogeneous with uniformly distributed small-sized lithium deposits are formed on the Li_{pce} electrode (Figure 7e). Once more, due to the presence of the Li-Zn intermetallic phase that increases the electronic and ionic conductivity at the particle surface and within the electrode bulk, the lithium deposits are better dispersed in the electrode volume and thus do not solely form at the surface (Figure 7e). This homogeneous deposition behavior also strongly reduces the pulverization of the electrodes and the fast degradation of the cell performance during the lithium electrodisolution (Figure 7f) and results in prolonged cycling stability. Therefore, it is likely that the Li-Zn intermetallic phase, when uniformly distributed at the surface of the lithium-powder particles (as a thin layer), directed favors the lithium electrodeposition in the elec-

trode bulk, thus also reducing the surface formation of the HSAL as observed for the unmodified electrodes.

Conclusions

In this work, the modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes was carried out using a solution of ZnI_2 in THF. The investigated lithium-powder based electrodes modified with ZnI_2 presented superior electrochemical characteristics as compared to the unmodified electrodes. Stable cycling performance for more than 300 cycles were shown in $\text{Li}_{pce}||\text{Li}_{pce}$ -symmetric cells, while the electrochemical behavior of the unmodified lithium-powder based electrodes deteriorated after only 50 cycles in $\text{Li}_p||\text{Li}_p$ -symmetric cells. Furthermore, the ZnI_2 modification was able to avoid the intrinsic problems of lithium-powder based electrode, i.e., uncontrolled lithium electrodisolution that led to inhomogeneous contact between lithium-metal particles and with the Cu-foil current collector during the electrochemical process.

It was also indicated that the modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes using a solution ZnI_2 in THF lowers the overvoltages during the electrochemical process. In addition, the improved electrochemical performance with stable cycling characteristics demonstrated in $Li_{pce}||NMC\ 622$ cells, further suggest that the presence of a Li-Zn intermetallic phase within the Li_{pce} electrode bulk homogenizes the flux of lithium-ions, thus better distributes the lithium deposits throughout the electrode.

Although the modification of the lithium-powder based electrodes with ZnI_2 was successful, further optimizations of the technique are necessary in order to further increase the active material utilization in the Li_{pce} electrodes. In general, such an approach could enable the use of lithium-powder based electrodes that are able to prevent detrimental reactions with the electrolyte, control the lithium electrodeposition morphology and decrease the electrode (cathode and anode) degradation. Furthermore, surface-coated lithium-powder based electrodes can enable the use of other battery systems, such as all solid state batteries (ASSBs), where the powder electrodes will avoid the issues created by the flat surfaces resulting in poor interfacial contact between the lithium anode and the solid electrolyte.

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ORCID

Martin Kolek <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7852-4064>

Peter Bieker <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4378-4805>

Marian Cristian Stan <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2654-9355>

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